

MISMATCH BETWEEN STEM SKILLS AND INDUSTRY DEMANDS: BASIS FOR CAREER FRAMEWORK FOR SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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Mismatch Between Stem Skills and Industry Demands: Basis for Career Framework for Senior High School

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Abstract

This research study explored the skills mismatch between STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) and industry demands as a basis for developing a career framework for Senior High School students. The aim of the study is to identify the gaps between the skills acquired through STEM education and skills required by industries, with the goal of informing the development of a career framework. The research methodology includes literature review, surveys, interviews with industry experts, and analysis of existing STEM skills. Finding suggests that there is a misalignment between the skills taught in Senior High School STEM program and the skills demanded by industries. Implications of this mismatch as discussed, and recommendations are provided for the design of a career framework that better prepares students for future careers in STEM related fields. The study highlights the importance of bridging the gap between education and industry demands to endure that Senior High School students are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed in the workplace.

Keywords: *skills mismatch, stem, senior high school, careers, career framework*

Introduction

Skills defined as the ability of an individual to perform a task or resolve a given problem at a level of proficiency. It can be acquired through different aspects such as education, trainings, and even experiences. There are different types of skills that can be categorized depending on its origin. Soft skills relate to interpersonal and communication abilities. It is more focused on effective communication, collaboration, and relationship-building. Hard skills are identified as measurable abilities than can be acquired through formal education, training, or On-the-job experience. It is measured easier that the soft skills as this is more job- specific and falls under the technical proficiencies. Personal skills also known as qualities or traits are more of an individual's character, behavior, and personality. This commonly inherent and can influence one's interaction, decision-making, and professional and personal success. Lastly, knowledge-based skills which commonly being acquired as well through education, training, or On-the-job experience focuses on concepts, theories, and principles (Van Echtelt, 2024).

These skills are what the Department of Education aims to develop in implementing the K to 12 programs as its new curriculum in the year 2013. It aims to develop the skills of the Filipino students by means of following the international standards of education by adding Senior High School years in the curriculum. One of the key goals of the K to 12 curriculum is to lessen the unemployment rate of the country by giving students ample time develop necessary skills needed in landing to a job. The mastery of competencies and skills for students will help them conquer the demands of labor market (Business Mirror, 2023).

In April of 2018, approximately 1.2 million SHS students graduated, and these students should be ready with employment as designed in the K to 12 curriculums. However, based on the research conducted by Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) in December the same year, it shows that three- quarters of the grade 12 students plan to proceed in higher education and there remaining of the fraction tend to proceed in joining workforce. (Lim, 2022) explained that labor market suggest that graduates of secondary education were unvalued and cannot secure jobs that fits their skills and abilities. There is a gap between the student's skills acquired in school and the market demands. A scenario in which promotes unemployment or underemployment for Senior High School graduates and there are implications that companies are still hesitant in hiring Senior High School. Primarily due to the reason that Senior High School graduates are not equipped to perform the duty of a certain role in a company. Pascual (2019) challenged schools to provide proof that SHS graduates are capable of employment after school to make sure that students are well trained and skilled which would be their foundation in entering the challenging labor community. In the same article, Fenix (2018) said they have no confidence that Senior High School graduates have the capacity to be employed.

On the other hand, Philippine Chamber of Commerce and Industry and other industry partners campaigned to revisit the qualification of their employees that will suite the skills intended for Senior High School graduates. It has been discussed that not all companies are aware with K to 12 program offerings which could result into stigma that Senior High School graduates are not yet ready or worst not employable. Yee (2018) mentioned that many companies only accepting applicants with at least two years in college.

One of the main reasons for unemployment or underemployment among Senior High School graduates is the mismatch between the skills they possess, and the skills demanded by the job market especially in areas where there is a high concentration of college graduates or where industries are not adequately developed. Employers often prioritize candidates with relevant work experience, leaving fresh graduates at a disadvantage. Insufficient career guidance and counseling services in Senior High School can contribute to unemployment or underemployment as students may not receive proper guidance on career options, job market trends, or the skills

needed to succeed in their chosen fields.

Cedefop (2018) discussed in the skills mismatch report conducted in Euro zone that there are 2 million job vacancies with 22% young candidates are unemployed. This is the result of shortage of qualified skilled candidates to join workforce. Competencies for STEM students were not being developed causing unemployment for its completers. Respondents to this study attended an interview and 1/3 of them did not receive any feedback from the employers. Those who gotten feedback were cited of insufficient level of STEM skills in which disqualify them for a job position. Employers are rearing towards experiences of an individual to fulfill the duties available in the labor market. Employers also pointed out the shortage of qualified candidates in IT and Engineering fields. Other companies recognize the issue that limit candidates to be employed such as companies may not recognize the skills and competence developed by students inside the school.

Overall, Senior High School graduates in the Philippines garnered a low employment rate in which the promotion of the Department of Education that students are job ready could be misleading. The researcher aims to assess the skills developed by Senior High School that will prepare them in joining workforce. The researcher also intends to identify career or job opportunities emerging nowadays for STEM Senior High School students. This is limited to the level of skills of students how can this be beneficial with the career framework that will be developed in this study. Given that STEM students are inclined in this study, it is also important to know if the skills and the demands of labor market are conniving and will result into a favorable scenario to both stakeholders. In this study, STEM Senior High School students will be given a clear path by means of a career framework highlighting the skills as well as the available job opportunities to which demands of labor market they fit in to.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the mismatch between STEM Senior High School students acquired while inside the school vs the industry demanded skills of various companies. This is giving emphasis on what is currently in place for STEM Senior High School and what are the demands outside. By this, the researcher will create a career framework that will serve as a guide to STEM Senior High School students in finding the most suitable career path after school. The following questions are sought to answer by the researcher:

1. What is the level of competencies or skillset do STEM Senior High School learners acquire while completing the curriculum inside the school?
2. What is the industry demanded skills and competencies of STEM learners in the labor market as qualifications in filling a job role?
3. What are the gaps causing skills mismatch between STEM Senior High School students and industry qualifications?
4. What is the proposed career framework for STEM Senior High School students?

Methodology

This section serves as a roadmap for how the research was conducted, detailing the specific steps taken to address research questions. This includes a clear and systematic explanation of the research design, including the selection of respondents and participants, data collection instruments, data analysis techniques, and any ethical considerations that were considered. This is essential for establishing the credibility and rigor of the research study, demonstrating the systematic approach taken to generate meaningful and trustworthy results.

Research Design

The researcher utilized the mixed-method descriptive research design to answer the research questions. In this method, the results gathered from the quantitative method, then it was supported with the qualitative method, which interpret the numerical findings through narrative data (Drauker, et al, 2020).

This method helped the researcher describe the level of skillset of STEM students and what they have acquired in completing Senior High School curriculum versus the industry demanded qualifications in filling a certain position. It also provided a detailed and accurate account of the existing conditions, relationships, or patterns within a specific context. Since this study was focused on the skills mismatch of STEM students and the industry demands, the descriptive research design was used to further justify the relationship of every variable obtained during the data gathering and formulated the career framework for Senior High School students.

In mixed-method descriptive research design, researcher employed a variety of data collection and data analysis techniques such as surveys and interviews. There are two (2) data sets that were collected in this study. First is coming from students in quantitative method which they were asked using a survey form to assess their level skills and competencies. Second, a qualitative method in a form of interviews with guide questions were conducted together with Human Resources or Recruitment Specialists in determining the qualifications and available opportunities for STEM students. These variables were utilized to draw situation and relationship in building a career framework for STEM students in Senior High School. The relationship of data sets presented can justify and answer the research questions in this study.

Participants

This research is composed of two (2) data sets gathered from both quantitative and qualitative methods. The quantitative data for this study was gathered from the respondents such as Grade 12 STEM Senior High School students of the Asia Source iCollege with a gender mix of twenty-five (25) pupils based on the data provided by the school, who were given a closed-ended questionnaire. The locale selected for this research is the Asia Source iCollege in Pasig that offers STEM strand in Senior High School. The school does not have any career framework that students can utilize in finding an available jobs for them in the labor market. The sample size for quantitative method was determined by the total number of students under the STEM program as stated above and the researcher utilized complete enumeration technique of respondents participated in the survey to identify the current skillset of Grade 12 STEM students of Asia Source iCollege.

On the other hand, the qualitative data were gathered from Human Resources and Recruitment Specialist looking for candidates in connection with opportunities available for STEM Senior High School. This will uncover job opportunities along with its qualification such as skills and competencies of Senior High School students. The researcher utilized the online job search platform, LinkedIn, gathered and identified five (5) participants. These participants are working as Human Resources or Recruitment Specialists of various businesses and accepted invitations for interviews were scheduled based on the availability of the participants. For their convenience, interviews were conducted online via video conferencing. Participants were selected using simple random sampling technique and the data presented will serve as the basis for the whole population (CFI Team, 2021). This is also to avoid researcher's biases in gathering data for this study. According to (Dworkin, 2012), there are accounts that suggest of having five (5) participants in a qualitative study is enough to help draw the picture of what is being questioned in a study and this is beneficial in the researchers study as the it will help in finding the skillset connection of STEM students as well as the gaps between the industry demands in terms of qualifications.

Instruments

Quantitative method in a form of closed-ended survey was utilized to twenty- five (25) Grade 12 STEM Senior High School students of Asia Source iCollege. The questionnaire includes 21st century skills that describe how applicable it is for students. A five (5) scale rating was utilized to identify the STEM students' level per skill. Rating scale as describe as follows: (5) Excellent, (4) Very Good, (3) Good, (2) Fair, (1) Poor. Questions were asked in line with the current skillset of STEM Senior High School students.

Qualitative method in a form of interviews with guided questions were conducted to five (5) Human Resources or Recruitment Specialists to further understand the demands of labor market. Guide questions include the skills that Human Resources or Recruitment Specialists are looking for a candidate. It also includes questions that will answer research questions 2, 3, and 4 such as gaps between student skills and industry demands.

The researcher created his own survey and interview questions which gone through pilot testing it has been reported that it has achieved reliability and validity which garnered the Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega > 0 and p value (Bartlett's) of $<.001$ respectively.

Procedure

The researcher personally visited the Asia Source iCollege and research instruments were presented to all respondents and the researcher explained how they will answer the material. Data gathering during this time was triangulated with an interview and observation. After which, participants were given thirty (30) minutes to go through and answer the survey form.

For interview participants, the researcher asked permission to record the call for documentation purposes. An overview and context of the interview were shared to each participant for them to know the purpose of this study. Interview duration lasted for half to an hour discussion depending on how the participants answered the questionnaires.

After successfully gathering the data, the researcher tabulated all answers from the survey responses and transcribed data based on the recorded interviews. The researcher secured that the number of participants and respondents were tallied based on the expected number of headcounts per method. All responses cannot be confirmed as valid or invalid as they were based on the understanding and experiences of the participants. A file was created to tabulate, and tallied responses used for data analysis in which provided clear connection and outcome based on the research questions.

Descriptive statistics was used in analyzing gathered quantitative data of the research in which the numerical representation of the results from survey were interpreted and present findings based on the statistical data. These methods helped the researcher gained insights, identify patterns, and make informed decisions of the current skillset of Grade 12 Senior High School and draw the gap with the demands of labor market in a meaningful way based on the data presented.

Thematic analysis was conducted for qualitative data to understand the demands of market labor in terms on finding qualified candidates for a certain job. Superordinate themes and subthemes were plotted with corresponding illustrative texts were presented. Data tables were utilized in tabulating both quantitative and qualitative data.

Ethical Considerations

Upon conducting this study, the researcher made aware all participants and respondents of the survey and interviews are voluntary participation. No rewards or return favor were imposed in completing the questionnaires and interviews. Participants were also be

given ample time to know the purpose of the study including the benefits, funding (if applicable) in a form of consent prior to joining the survey and interview conducted. This study aims to identify the gaps between the competencies of STEM Senior High School students of the Asia Source iCollege and the demands of the labor market in line with the qualifications needed to secure a job or career after school. This study can be useful in developing a career framework that an academe can execute in preparation of seeking employment upon completion of the curriculum.

The researcher secured the anonymity of the respondents in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of the Philippines and all data collected are treated utmost confidentiality. Respondents and participants were informed about their right to be informed, object to processing, access and rectify, suspend, or withdraw their personal data, and be indemnified in case of damages pursuant to the provision to Republic Act No. 10173 of the Philippines also known as Data Privacy Act of 2012 and its corresponding Implementing Rules and Regulations. Any potential harm to the respondents, may it be physical, psychological, social should be kept in absolute minimum. Results of this study represents solely the researcher, and any forms of plagiarism is unacceptable.

Results and Discussion

In this section, the analysis of the data collected aims to provide a deeper understanding of the research questions posited. The results are presented in a clear and organized manner, highlighting key trends, patters, and relationship identified during the study. This contributed to the broader academic discourse within the mismatch between STEM skills and industry demands that resulted in formulating a career framework.

The result of these surveys provides a clear understanding on the level of competencies or skillset that STEM Senior High School students acquired while completing the curriculum.

1.What is the level of competencies or skillset do STEM Senior High School learners acquire while completing the curriculum inside the school?

Table 1. *Level of Critical Thinking Skills*

<i>Critical Thinking Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can analyze, evaluate, and interpret information effectively to make informed decisions and solve complex problems.	3.60	.82	Very good
I can question and examine assumptions, evidence, and arguments to arrive at logical and well-reasoned conclusions.	3.56	.82	Very good
I can be open-minded, considering different perspectives, and being able to effectively communicate and defend one's own ideas.	4.08	.76	Very good
I can navigate complex situations, solve problems, and make sound decisions in various aspects of life.	3.64	.70	Very good
I can breakdown complex information into smaller parts to understand the underlying components and relationships.	3.52	.77	Very good
I can understand and explain the meaning and significance of information or data.	3.68	.99	Very good
Total	3.68	.56	Very good

The weighted mean of critical thinking score for the participants in this study was 3.68, indicating a high level of critical thinking skill overall. Notably, item such as "I can be open-minded, considering different perspectives, and being able to effectively communicate and defend one's own ideas." (Item 3) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

Exemplary STEM high schools prioritize the development of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, and self-regulation, emphasizing knowledge construction over passive information consumption (Stehle & Burton, 2019). This pedagogical approach fosters self-directed learning and resilience, essential for adapting to dynamic technological landscapes.

Table 2. *Level of Creative Thinking Skills*

<i>Creative Thinking Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can generate innovative ideas, exploring new possibilities, and approaching challenges with originality.	3.60	.91	Very good
I am open to new ideas, perspectives, and approaches.	4.28	.68	Excellent
I can generate unique and novel ideas or solutions.	3.40	.76	Very good
I can generate a large quantity of ideas without judgement or criticism.	3.40	.71	Very good
I can develop and expand on initial ideas to create more detailed and refined concepts.	3.52	.71	Very good
Total	3.64	.57	Very good

The weighted mean of creative thinking score for the participants in this study was 3.64, indicating a high level of creative thinking skill overall. Notably, item such as "I am open to new ideas, perspectives, and approaches." (Item 2) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

Research conducted by Khalil et al. (2023) investigated the influence of STEM-based curricula on high school students' creative thinking. Their findings indicated significant improvements in creative thinking skills, particularly in fluency, flexibility, and

originality, facilitated by interdisciplinary instruction and project-based learning. Further studies have underscored the efficacy of work immersion programs in enhancing students' technical and social skills, aligning their competencies with industry standards and bolstering their employability. For instance, research evaluating STEM high school programs across various states demonstrated the substantial benefits of immersion experiences in industry settings.

Table 3. *Level of Collaborating Skills*

<i>Collaborating Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can work with others to achieve a common goal or objectives.	4.20	.82	Excellent
I can share information, feedback, and updates with the team members to ensure everyone is on the same page.	4.48	.65	Excellent
I can work in a harmonious and supportive manner to achieve shared goals.	3.96	.93	Very good
I organize and align efforts to ensure that tasks are completed efficiently and effectively.	4.04	.79	Very good
I am willing to negotiate and find common ground when there are differing opinions or perspective.	3.88	.97	Very good
I actively participate and contribute unique skills, knowledge, and expertise.	3.80	.96	Very good
Total	4.06	.67	Very good

The weighted mean of collaborating score for the participants in this study was 4.06, indicating a high level of collaborating skill overall. Notably, item such as "I organize and align efforts to ensure that tasks are completed efficiently and effectively." (Item 4) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in in this aspect.

Contemporary STEM curricula recognize the importance of soft skills like communication, teamwork, and problem-solving, integrating them through collaborative projects and group activities to prepare students for collaborative work environments (UNESCO, 2018).

Table 4. *Level of Communicating Skills*

<i>Communicating Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can convey ideas, information, and feedback clearly and concisely.	3.48	.82	Very good
I am paying attention to the speaker, understanding their message, and providing feedback to demonstrate understanding.	3.96	.89	Very good
I understand and consider the emotions, perspectives, and experiences of others when communicating	4.12	.67	Very good
I use body language, facial expressions, gestures, and tone of voice to convey additional meaning and emotions.	4.04	.79	Very good
I provide and receive constructive feedback to improve communication and ensure mutual understanding.	3.64	.70	Very good
I can adjust my communication style, tone, or approach based on the needs and preferences of the audience.	4.00	.81	Very good
Total	3.87	.49	Very good

The weighted mean of communicating score for the participants in this study was 3.87, indicating a high level of communication skill overall. Notably, item such as "I understand and consider the emotions, perspectives, and experiences of others when communicating." (Item 3) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

McGunagle and Zizka (2020) underscore the significance of soft skills in the workplace. According to their study, essential employability skills include teamwork, self-motivation, verbal communication, problem-solving, and proactivity. These skills play a pivotal role in fostering effective collaboration and driving innovation within organizations.

Table 5. *Level of Information Literacy*

<i>Information Literacy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can locate, evaluate, and effectively use information from various sources.	3.80	.91	Very Good
I recognize when information is needed and defining the scope of the information required.	3.64	.76	Very Good
I know how to effectively search for and retrieve information using variety of sources and tools.	3.72	1.02	Very Good
I can assess the credibility, accuracy, relevance, and bias of information sources to determine their reliability.	3.84	.75	Very Good
I can organize and synthesize information in a meaningful way to facilitate understanding and use.	3.68	.85	Very Good
I respect intellectual property rights and using information ethically and responsibly.	4.12	.88	Very Good
Total	3.80	.67	Very Good

The weighted mean of information literacy score for the participants in this study was 3.80, indicating a high level of information literacy skill overall. Notably, item such as "I respect intellectual property rights and using information ethically and responsible." (Item 6) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

Work immersion programs intended to provide practical experience are often not aligned with students' fields of study, leading to graduates lacking the necessary hands-on experience required by employers in STEM fields (Bustamante, 2019).

Table 6. *Level of Media Literacy*

<i>Media Literacy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can access, analyze, evaluate, and create media in variety of forms.	3.72	.84	Very good
I can find and access wide range of media sources and formats	3.76	.88	Very good
I can critically examine media messages, content, and techniques, to understand their intended meanings and potential biases.	3.92	.70	Very good
I can understand the underlying messages, themes, and values conveyed through media content.	3.60	.76	Very good
I can produce and share media content responsibly and ethically.	3.76	.88	Very good
I can assess the credibility, accuracy, and reliability of media sources and information.	3.96	.68	Very good
Total	3.79	.61	Very good

The weighted mean of media literacy score for the participants in this study was 3.79, indicating a high level of media literacy overall. Notably, item such as “I can assess the credibility, accuracy, and reliability of media sources and information.” (Item 6) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

A study exploring the digital literacy of STEM senior high school students emphasized the importance of integrating digital skills into the STEM curriculum. While students were adept at using basic digital tools, the study suggested a need for more advanced training to meet the demands of higher education and industry. (Baterna, Mina, & Rogayan, 2020).

Table 7. *Level Technology Literacy*

<i>Technology Literacy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can effectively use and understand technology tools and systems.	4.04	.84	Very good
I am proficient in using digital tools, applications, and platforms for communication, collaboration, and productivity.	3.80	.76	Very good
I can find, evaluate, and use information effectively and ethically in a digital environment.	3.72	.84	Very good
I understand how to protect personal information, devices, and networks from online threats and risks.	4.24	.72	Very good
I can apply critical-thinking skills to assess the credibility, reliability, and implications of technology-related information and sources.	3.64	.95	Very good
I recognize and address ethical issues related to technology use, such as privacy, data security, and digital rights.	3.84	.85	Very good
Total	3.88	.67	Very good

The weighted mean of technological literacy score for the participants in this study was 3.88, indicating a high level of technological literacy skill overall. Notably, item such as " I understand how to protect personal information, devices, and networks from online threats and risks." (Item 4) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

According to Alcantara (2023), higher education institutions in the Philippines are encouraged to focus on developing competencies in advanced engineering, robotics, and cybersecurity. These areas are crucial for maintaining competitiveness in a technology-driven economy. Additionally, given the rapid pace of technological change, the ability to continuously learn and adapt is critical. Workers need to engage in lifelong learning to keep their skills relevant and up to date.

Table 8. *Level of Flexibility Skills*

<i>Flexibility</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can adapt and adjust to changing circumstances and situations.	3.84	.62	Very good
I am receptive to novel concepts, perspectives, or solutions that may differ from one's own beliefs or assumptions.	3.40	.82	Very good
I can adjust to one's strategies, plans, or actions in response to unexpected challenges or opportunities.	3.64	.76	Very good
I can embrace unconventional and innovative approaches to problem- solving and decision-making.	3.32	.85	Very good
I can bounce back from setbacks or failures by learning from experiences and adjusting one's approach accordingly.	3.88	.78	Very good
I can work closely with others and being willing to compromise or consider different viewpoints to achieve common goals.	4.00	.87	Very good
Total	3.68	.59	Very good

The weighted mean of flexibility score for the participants in this study was 3.68, indicating a high level of flexibility skill overall. Notably, item such as "I can work closely with others and being willing to compromise or consider different viewpoints to achieve

common goals.” (Item 6) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

Research conducted by Khalil et al. (2023) investigated the influence of STEM-based curricula on high school students' creative thinking. Their findings indicated significant improvements in creative thinking skills, particularly in fluency, flexibility, and originality, facilitated by interdisciplinary instruction and project-based learning. Further studies have underscored the efficacy of work immersion programs in enhancing students' technical and social skills, aligning their competencies with industry standards and bolstering their employability. For instance, research evaluating STEM high school programs across various states demonstrated the substantial benefits of immersion experiences in industry settings.

Table 9. *Level of Initiative*

<i>Initiative</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can take actions and make decisions without being prompted.	3.44	.92	Very good
I can anticipate needs or opportunities and take actions before being asked or required to do so.	3.68	.80	Very good
I take ownership of tasks, projects, or goals and seeing them through to completion.	3.76	.88	Very good
I can think creatively and innovatively to generate new ideas or solutions.	3.68	.80	Very good
I overcome obstacles, setbacks, or challenges with determination and perseverance.	3.84	.75	Very good
I inspire and motivate others to act and achieve common goals.	3.84	.90	Very good
Total	3.71	.65	Very good

The weighted mean of initiative score for the participants in this study was 3.71, indicating a high level of initiative skill overall. Notably, items such as "I overcome obstacles, setbacks, or challenges with determination and perseverance." (Item 5) and "I inspire and motivate others to act and achieve common goals." (Item 6) received a particularly high mean scores, indicating strength in this aspect.

Rawlings (2022) discussed initiative as an ability of an individual to be proactive and working without being to do so. People possessed initiative amplifies good thinking for themselves and taking accountability to every action. It is also called self-management skills as it results into continuous learning and growing. This means that an individual is going beyond what is expected and doing extra miles on their work. It important to an organization to have employees with initiative since they tend to resolve things that some may not notice of worth solving for.

Table 10. *Level of Social Skills*

<i>Social Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can effectively interact and communicate with others in various social situation.	3.72	.98	Very good
I can express thoughts, ideas, and emotions clearly and effectively, both verbal and non-verbal.	3.60	.87	Very good
I listen attentively to others, showing empathy, and understanding their feelings and prospective.	4.04	.61	Very good
I have the capacity to understand and share the feelings and experiences of others, showing compassion and considerations.	3.80	.76	Very good
I can manage and resolve conflicts or disagreements in a constructive and respectful manner.	3.60	.76	Very good
I can work effectively with others towards common goal, sharing responsibilities, and respecting diverse viewpoints.	4.04	.79	Very good
Total	3.80	.56	Very good

The weighted mean of social skill score for the participants in this study was 3.80, indicating a high level of social skill overall. Notably, items such as "I listen attentively to others, showing empathy, and understanding their feelings and prospective." (Item 3) and "I can work effectively with others towards common goal, sharing responsibilities, and respecting diverse viewpoints." (Item 6) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect. Research conducted by Khalil et al. (2023) investigated the influence of STEM-based curricula on high school students' creative thinking. Their findings indicated significant improvements in creative thinking skills, particularly in fluency, flexibility, and originality, facilitated by interdisciplinary instruction and project-based learning. Further studies have underscored the efficacy of work immersion programs in enhancing students' technical and social skills, aligning their competencies with industry standards and bolstering their employability. For instance, research evaluating STEM high school programs across various states demonstrated the substantial benefits of immersion experiences in industry settings.

Table 11. *Level of Productivity*

<i>Productivity</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can efficiently complete and achieve goals.	3.80	.87	Very good
I can prioritize tasks, set goals, and allocating time effectively to accomplish objectives.	3.68	.75	Very good
I can concentrate on important task and minimize distractions to maintain high levels of concentration and performance.	3.56	.96	Very good
I stay motivated and engaged to sustain productivity levels and achieve desired results.	3.56	.96	Very good
I create systems and structure to streamline workflows, reduce inefficiencies, and optimize processes.	3.28	.89	Very good
I work effectively with others to leverage collective skills and resources for enhanced productivity.	3.52	.77	Very good
Total	3.57	.67	Very good

The weighted mean of productivity score for the participants in this study was 3.57, indicating a high level of productivity skill overall. Notably, item such as “I can efficiently complete and achieve goals.” (Item 1) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

Globally, the demand for STEM graduates is very high. Hill, Corbett & St. Rose (2020) mentioned that many countries in the world face the task of recruiting more individuals into STEM industries. However, students’ interest in STEM careers is declining. Several studies reported a decline in student engagement with STEM and subsequent choices to pursue STEM related careers. Undoubtedly, STEM had contributed vital importance in building the nation’s productivity. In Australia, the prevailing view is that the workforce and economy require additional STEM skills and knowledge to support the nation’s productivity and prosperity and thus remain competitive on the international platform (Siekmann & Korbel, 2019).

Relatively, a strong focus was also given by the STEM-related industries in the United States just to alleviate the number of students engaging in postsecondary participation in STEM education (Baber, 2019). Moreover, Malaysia is in dire need of a workforce in the year 2020 (Vijaindren, 2018). But despite the government’s commitment, Malaysia still had been struggling to meet the human capital demand that is necessary for 2020. In recent years, STEM field enrollees had continued to decline (Halim & Meerah, 2021).

Table 12. *Level of Leadership Skill*

<i>Leadership Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can inspire and guide individuals or teams towards common goal.	3.56	.87	Very good
I can set a clear and compelling vision for future and inspiring others to work towards that vision.	3.48	.92	Very good
I can articulate goals, expectations, and feedback clearly and effectively to ensure understanding and alignment.	3.60	.96	Very good
I can make informed and timely decisions based on available information and considering the impact on stakeholders.	3.72	1.02	Very good
I understand and consider the needs, perspective, and feelings of others to build trust and foster collaboration.	3.88	1.05	Very good
I can persuade and motivate others to act and achieve shared objectives.	3.68	.90	Very good
Total	3.65	.80	Very good

The weighted mean of leadership score for the participants in this study was 3.65, indicating a high level of leadership skill overall. Notably, item such as “I understand and consider the needs, perspective, and feelings of others to build trust and foster collaboration.” (Item 5) received a particularly high mean score, indicating strength in this aspect.

Pandey (2024) suggest that leadership is about challenging the status quo. Individuals who possessed leadership skills are influential and can make a difference to others. They are an example of what needs to be done and at the same time someone that the team can rely on. Leadership skills also includes analyzing and assessing situations to achieve better results. Having these skills comes with a set of responsibilities and can result into both positive and negative impacts.

Table 13. *Overall Skills Level of STEM Students*

<i>Skillset</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Critical Thinking Skills	3.68	.56	Very Good
Creative Thinking Skills	3.64	.57	Very Good
Collaborating Skills	4.06	.67	Very Good
Communicating Skills	3.87	.49	Very Good
Information Literacy	3.80	.67	Very Good
Media Literacy	3.79	.61	Very Good
Technology Literacy	3.88	.67	Very Good
Flexibility	3.68	.59	Very Good
Initiative	3.71	.65	Very Good
Social Skills	3.80	.56	Very Good
Productivity	3.57	.67	Very Good
Leadership Skills	3.65	.80	Very Good
Total	3.76	.73	Very Good

The weighted mean of the overall score for the participants in this study was 3.76, indicating a high-level skillset. The highest contributing skill is collaborating (M=4.06). These results suggest that participants in this study demonstrated particularly strong skills in this aspect.

In the study of (Cannon, 2019), it was mentioned how important collaboration is when it comes to completing a task. This as aspect as the highest skill of STEM Senior High School implies that they can work closely with other members of the group with the intent to share, learn, and contribute to achieve the common goal. In this manner, other skills could follow such as communication skills and social skills triangulated with technology and information literacy. These skills are the top skills as listed above are combination of

both soft and hard skills with mean of 3.8 and above.

Despite of the identified skills mismatch between the STEM students and industry demanded skills, respondents delivered a high-level skillset based on their own personal assessment. This suggests that the result of the survey is somehow related to Dunning-Kruger effect. (Sreenivas, Shawna, 2024) discussed Dunning-Kruger as cognitive bias in which an individual tends to overestimate how much they good at on a certain area. Good students often underestimate themselves where in the other hand, challenged students are more likely to overestimates their skills. Some causes of Dunning-Kruger effect are having limited, or lack of skills required to perform a certain task, relying on intuition instead of reliable data, easy decision-making, and obsolete knowledge because of not upskilling.

Dunning-Kruger effect could be avoided if an individual could recognize his or her own biases and increasing self-awareness of his own abilities. In relation to this study, a career framework helps an individual to assess personal skills and match it with the industry demands to draw a clear path of career opportunities available in the labor market. This could also avoid any issues in line with underemployment as the common factors between the students’ skills and industry demands would be the basis of landing a job

2. What is the industry demanded skills and competencies of STEM learners in the labor market as qualifications in filling a job role?

Table 14. *STEM Skills vs Industry Demands*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Illustrative Text</i>
		<i>“I think that has an impact kung ano yung ranking po dun sa skills that you have provided. So, number 1 for me definitely would be critical thinking.” -P1</i>
Cognitive Skills	Critical Thinking	Translation: I think that has an impact on what ranking of skills you have provided. So, number 1 for me definitely would be critical thinking. <i>“Most of my top skill, that I’m looking for, for a candidate, considering most of the positions based on my professional tenure ship, it’s really more of the entry level. And for the entry level, I would say, I’m really into the critical thinking of the candidate. -P2</i>
	Attention to Detail	<i>“So, we’re really after the soft skills, primarily strong attention to details talaga. -P2</i>
Working with others	Initiative	<i>“Okay. Basically, yes. Flexibility, initiative, willingness to learn.” -P1</i>
	Good Communication Skill	<i>“So that really comes in, the communication skills comes in. So, I think those are just the skillset that would be required for such role.”-P3</i>
Self-efficacy	Flexibility	<i>“They should carry and show their willingness to be more flexible in the position that they are applying for” -P4</i>
Technology Skills	Technology Proficient	<i>“So, if I will be the one to evaluate a candidate, I would like him or her to be a technology literacy”- P5</i>

As shown in Table 14, participants of the interview stated the top skills needed for STEM Senior High School students needed when applying for work. Some of the skills as stated by the participants are Critical Thinking, Flexibility, Initiative, Attention to Detail, Good Communication Skills, and Technology Proficient.

It was suggested on this study that cognitive skills are highly demanded by industry partners in which critical thinking and attention to details are much needed in landing a job. Nji (2023) highlighted that Critical Thinking as a core skill in which an individual can evaluate, conceptualize, question, and scrutinize information presented. It is a critical skill that Human Resources or Recruitment Specialist were looking to a candidate when filling out available positions in the industry.

Attention to details talks about how meticulous an individual with data as well as in-depth interpretation and uncovering underlying concerns of the issue involve. Hopgood (2024) discussed that attention to details refers to behavioral propensity in which people work with thoroughness, precision, and reliability when accomplishing a task. It is important to have these skills as the credibility of the company could be at stake when things do not work well based on the reliable sources available.

Another skillset that Human Resources were looking at is how an individual can work with others. This includes initiative and good communication skills. While technical skills are crucial, soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving are equally important. Many STEM programs fail to integrate these skills into the curriculum, leaving students ill-prepared for the collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of modern workplaces (Andrews & Higson, 2018).

Additionally, students on this study showed good communication skills where they can understand and consider the emotions, perspectives, and experiences of others when communicating. Obravo (2022) explained how crucial communication skills is to the success of any business. It is how an employee interacts with one another in fulfilling their daily job. Having good communication skills could reduce workplace problems and could result to a better performance at work.

Flexibility is the skill in which an individual can adapt and adjust to changing circumstances and situation. It is the ability to be receptive to novel concepts, perspectives, or solutions that may differ from one’s owns beliefs or assumptions. As a result in this study, students can work closely with others and being willing to compromise or consider different viewpoint to achieve common goals. Being flexible could result into increasing job satisfaction, leads to variety of careers, and helps in landing a job (4 Corner Resources, 2022).

Furthermore, Technology Literacy took its place in this study as Human Resources were considering high demand on this skill. This is the ability of the student to understand how to protect personal information, devices, and networks from online threats and risks. The study also suggests that students can effectively use and understand technology tools and systems. This skill helps students to improve communication and collaboration by means of variety of digital tools like emails, messaging, and virtual conferencing. It also enhances productivity and efficiency with the help of tools and software than reduced the time of work and eliminating manual processes. Technology literacy also paved way for an individual to access information and resources helping them being informed and being agile in decision-making (PMS Consulting, 2023).

In relation to the skills of STEM Students, participants have provided a set of skills that candidates should have when joining the labor market. As stated in the top skills of STEM students, both the school and the industry regarded communication skills and technology literacy are the important skills that for STEM students. Companies tend to give more importance on the soft skills as technical skills can be transferred to an individual via training and development plans.

Table 15. Available Careers for STEM Students

Superordinate Themes	Subthemes	Illustrative Text
Entry level roles	Customer Services	“if in case, you will be hiring those people that are covered by the STEM fields, most likely, they will be on a customer service department with Sophos.” – P5 “specifically for STEM, probably would be data entry. Servicing roles, servicing similar to customer service, pero (but more) ma- specific sya to banking products.”-P2
	Production Operators, Technician, Material Handlers	“we have production operators, technician, and material handlers. So yun po yung (this is the) top na career opportunities we can offer for STEM”-P1
Emerging Technology Specializations	Engineering Landscape	“For now, the career opportunities that will be available for the labor market for the STEM strand will be IT positions, engineering, engineers, property engineers, programmers, electricians, on what I understand for the strand of STEM”-P4
	Information Technology Careers	“And on the nature of education, I think they are fit more on the IT side as well.-P5
	Social Media Manager	“If you are considering social media management as part of the technology, I think it's one thing that I think you can consider. We can consider as available in the labor market.” -P3

Table 15 represents the career opportunities when a career framework has been implemented intended for STEM Senior High School students. Some of the career opportunities available as share by industry partners are Customer Services, Production Operators, Technician, Material Handlers, IT and Engineering Career Landscape, and Social Media Manager.

Given that the matching skills for STEM Senior High School students and industry demands are Communication and Technology Literacy, it was suggested that students are fit with entry level roles such as Customer Service and other related field in servicing. This is common with Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) wherein there are several lines on business that STEM students can join with such as healthcare, telecommunication, insurance, and other related to the field. As students suggest that they do have good communication skills, being with customer service field include handling queries, technical, support, and resolving issues (Panghal, 2024).

There are emerging careers for STEM Senior High School students in the field of manufacturing as suggested during the interview. Some of these opportunities are in production such as operators which requires a skill in modern technology as automations are present in some companies for better productivity. In an average, 94% of teachers in the United States suggests that manufacturing jobs support middle class and boost their standard of living. At the same discussion, manufacturing improves national security and even narrow wealth gap (Student Research Foundation, 2023).

Some opportunities suggested are with Information Technology and engineering landscape. Known to be a fast-growing career in the field of Information Technology are technician, service desk support, and other cyber related activities. Opportunities in this field are Data Scientist (35.8%), Information Security Analyst (34.7%), Web Developer (30.3%), Software Developer (26%), Operations Research Analyst (23%) increase from 2021.

These are only few of tech opportunities that STEM students could participate with. This also concluded with the ever-evolving technology nowadays (Preston, 2023). Careers in social media are also a consideration. It offers diverse opportunities to students since there are variety of tasks that could be done via social media such as content creation and management, social media marketing, influencer partnership, and data analysis. It is relevant nowadays are young student tend to explore most of the time online thru different social media platforms (Admin, 2024).

Table 16. *Careers and Qualifications for STEM Students*

Job Roles	Positions	Qualifications
Entry level roles	Customer Services (specialization in Telecommunications, Health Services, Insurance)	Act as a liaison officer within the organization.
	Chat Services	Proficient in desktop applications Strong verbal and written communication skills and documentation.
	Data Entry and Management	Critical judgement and effective decision-making.
	Production Operators	Analytical and technical skills
	Technicians	Computer Literate
	Material Handlers	Good oral and written communication
	IT Service Desk	Good oral and written communications
Emerging Technology Specializations	Technical Support	Technical knowledge on basic software and hardware
	Social Media Manager	Proficiency in online and social media strategy
	Lead Generation	Good written and communication skills Multitasking and decision-making skills

Table 16 represents the available careers and qualification for STEM students. This has been drawn as the result of this study that helps in development of the career framework for Senior High School students. There are steps to follow when identifying the right career path for students. This includes the intervention of students in skills assessment and determining the trends of the labor market which resulted to the suitable careers for STEM Senior High School Students. By having the career framework, it serves as a guide for students in increasing their self-awareness and identifying their strengths and areas for improvement.

3. What are the gaps causing skills mismatch between STEM Senior High School students and industry qualifications?

Table 17. *Gaps Causing Skills Mismatch*

Superordinate Themes	Subthemes	Illustrative Text
Qualification Challenges	Absence of an educational degree	<p>“And somewhat, nagiging stagnant. It's because since they don't have that degree.”-P1 Translation: And somewhat it become stagnant. “Some of the employers were looking for someone who has a college degree. That's the reality in the corporate world.” -P4 “So yun pa yung talagang kailangan nilang mas matutunan, yung actual working. Actual working, probably ma'am busog na busog sila sa theory pero yung application medyo kulang kasi due to pandemic pa rin.” -P2 Translation: So that is really what they need to learn, the actual working. Actual working, probably ma'am they are full of theory, but the application is not quite enough probably still because of pandemic.</p>
	Limited Practical Experience	<p>“So, they have a lot of theories but in practice, somewhat limited. So, sometimes they cannot support that theory because they did not experience that. So, they are just referring according to the documentation that they have online” P5 “I believe mas limited yung exposure nila as compared to college graduates. Mas limited yung hours nila. They do OJT, they do internship. So medyo mas hirap sila mag-adapt sa aspetong yun” -P3 Translation: I believe that they have limited exposure as compared to college graduates. They have limited hours. They do OJT, they do internship. So, it is difficult for them to adapt on that aspect.</p>
	Lack of Communication Skill Mismatched Abilities and Expectations	<p>“Because some of the students right now in senior high school, they have lack of communication when it comes to corporate world.” - P3 “So, parang (seems) they are more into demanding a competitive salary, but they don't have that necessary skills or enough skills to fulfill the duty” - P4 “I think it would be more on lack of appropriate attitude siguro (probably) and values for the kind of work” – P5</p>
	Lack of appropriate attitude	

Table 17 shows the common causes of skills mismatch of between the STEM Senior High School and industry demands. Participants mentioned that some of the causes of skills mismatch are the following: (1) Absence of an Educational Degree, Limited Practical Experience, Lack of Communication Skills, Mismatch Abilities and Expectations, and Lack of appropriate attitude.

Yee (2018) shared that other companies tend to accept applicants with at least two years of college education. Employee qualifications of companies are intended for those with higher education and only limited opportunities were seen for Senior High School graduates. Some companies are hesitant to accept Senior High School graduates as schools failed to show proof that the curriculum provides adequate learning for student Valencia, (2019)

Participants also suggested that STEM Senior High School students are good in theory but falling behind with practical application. They also suggest that students have limited exposure to the real-life experiences while at school. It was also highlighted that because

of the pandemic, students were not given enough time to practice the skills that they have acquired in school. Fenix (2018) strongly support that Senior High School graduates does not have enough skills to take part of the corporate world. Skills and competencies are lacking in a way that those with college degree are more preferred by employers.

It was also highlighted the lack of communication of students as observed during the participants interview experiences. As stated on this study Obravo (2022) explained how crucial communication skills is to the success of any business. This is a Dunning-Kruger effect in which students tend to overestimate their skills which is the other way how industry assess.

Additionally, STEM Senior High School candidates tend to demand for a competitive in which Human Resources do not see the value as students tend to have only limited skills to fulfill job roles. Another factor is the attitude of the candidates. Human Resources have this idea of hire for attitude and train for skills. As discussed previously, both soft and hard skills are beneficial in a workplace. This factor falls under the character development of an individual.

4. What is the proposed career framework for STEM Senior High School students?

As a result of this study, Figure 1 below represents the Career Framework for Senior High School students. This will serve as the roadmap in landing a career that is tailored to the skills and industry demands. This cover all individual, group involve as state in the significance of the study.

Figure 1. Career Framework for Senior High School

First step is to identify the level of skills of STEM students. This is to know in which areas they are good at and to identify the current situation of STEM students. Reiterating that self-awareness as stated in Dunning-Kruger effect could help an individual understand his or her abilities. This is also a good start to set personal goals and development aligned with the career objectives of the student.

After understanding one's skills, it is good to know the demands of the labor market as well to see in which areas an individual can join with. This includes the available job in the labor market, matching personal skills assessment with the industry demands. In this manner, students can identify the areas that they can improve with to secure that career opportunity they are aiming for.

Gaps between STEM students' skills and industry demands can now be drawn which could be a basis of future development or upskilling. Some of gaps could be controllable factors which could be developed by further training or upskilling while factor such as higher educational attainment during the process is somewhat uncontrollable. By this, students can do the process of elimination in which some career opportunities that requires higher education or other uncontrollable factors could be eliminated.

Development plans are the upskilling part for the students. Once the areas for improvement and gaps have been identified, it is now time to develop the skills needed for career opportunities. This will give students time to be more familiarize with the trends and necessary skills in joining labor workforce. After doing so, they can go back with the skills assessment and go through the process again.

And a result of a comprehensive process by utilizing this career framework, STEM students can now identify career opportunities that tailor fit their skills available in the labor market. This would help them identify their strengths and weaknesses. And it helps them uncover other potentials by upskilling and future developments. The research questions presented in this study helped the researcher with the development of the career framework as it were answered with the means of identifying the skills of the students, identify the industry demanded skills, learn the gaps between students and industry, and formulate a reasonable basis of development plans for upskilling. Therefore, a process has been drawn and formulated a career framework that will help students identify the right career

choice tailored to their skills and industry demands.

Discussion

The findings of the study were summarized according to the research questions.

1. What is the level of competencies or skillset do STEM Senior High School learners acquire while completing the curriculum inside the school?

The weighted mean of the overall score for the participants in this study was 3.76, indicating high level skillset for STEM Senior High School students. The highest contributing skills is Collaborating ($M = 4.06$). These results suggest that respondents in this study demonstrated particularly strong skills in this aspect. This indicate that STEM Senior High School students can work with others to achieve a common goal or objectives. They can also share information, feedback, and updates with the team members to ensure everyone is on the same page. Working harmoniously and in a supportive manner to achieve shared goals. This also includes their willingness to negotiate and find common ground when there are differing opinions or perspective. It also suggests that students can actively participate and contribute unique skills, knowledge, and expertise. Above all, students can organize and align efforts to ensure that tasks are completed efficiently and effectively.

Second highest skills of the STEM Senior High School that shows high level of competency was Technology Literacy ($M = 3.88$) which also suggest that students are understand how to protect personal information, devices, and networks from online threats and risks. According to the study of (Galve, 2023), students are making significant improvement in terms of Technology Literacy skills, and they continuously acquire and improve with the ever evolving cyberworld. This includes proficiency in using digital tools, applications and platforms for communication, collaboration, and productivity. It also suggests that students can effectively use and understand technology tools and systems.

Another factor that involves Technology Literacy among STEM Senior High School students is their ability to find, evaluate, and use information effectively and ethically in a digital environment. This also involves critical-thinking skills to assess the credibility, reliability, and implications of technology-related information and resources. Ethical issues related to technology use, such as privacy, data security, and digital rights were also included with this high skills of STEM Senior High School students.

Third top skill of STEM Senior High School students is communicating ($M=3.87$). (Kusumawardhani, et al., 2019) studied the communication skills among the Senior High School students and it shows that the level of communication is just enough. This includes their ability to express ideas, communicate data process and analysis, ability to conclude research and formulate conclusions from the set of data, presentation of figure in an experiment, ability to utilize model of relations using international symbols and standards.

Overall, STEM Senior High School shows high level of skillset that could be beneficial when joining the labor workforce.

2. What is the industry demanded skills and competencies of STEM learners in the labor market as qualifications in filling a job role?

Based on the conducted interviews among the industry experts in terms of Human Resources and Recruitment, the following skills are the top skills that STEM Senior High School students should have to join the labor workforce: (1) Critical Thinking, (2) Flexibility and Initiative, (3) Attention to Detail, (4) Good Communication Skill, and (5) Technology Proficient). This suggests that for STEM Senior High School students secure a career in the industry, these skills should be their foundation as other aspects can be developed as they progress within the organization. Two (2) of the participants of the interview mentioned that Critical Thinking should be the most skills that a candidate should have when they interviewed candidates.

As a result, candidates should be open-minded, considering different perspectives, and being able to effectively communicate and defend one's own ideas. It also entails that candidates should have the ability to understand and explain the meaning and significance of information or data as well as ability to navigate complex situations, solve problems, and make sound decisions in various aspects of life. This also includes the ability to analyze, interpret information effectively to make informed decisions and solve complex problems. Lastly, one's ability to question and examine assumptions, evidence, and arguments to arrive at logical and well-reasoned conclusions as well as the ability to breakdown complex information into smaller parts to understand the underlying components and relationships.

3. What are the gaps causing skills mismatch between STEM Senior High School students and industry qualifications?

In finding out the gaps that causing the skills mismatch between STEM Senior High School students an industry qualification, participants shared that there are qualification challenges and competency discrepancy between these entities. It suggests that absence of an educational degree, limited practical experiences, and lack of communication skills hinders STEM Senior High in fulfilling a position in the labor market. Subsequently, mismatched abilities and expectations as well as lack of appropriate attitude also contributed to the gaps between skills and industry qualifications.

4. What is the proposed career framework for STEM Senior High School students?

As a result of this study, a career framework was drawn as a guide of STEM Senior High School students intended to join the labor

workforce available in the market. Some of the listed career opportunities are entry level roles which requires skills to handle customer services, production operators, technicians, and material handlers. There are also emerging technology specializations under the Information Technology and Engineering career landscape as well as Social Media Manager. These are all based on the results of the interview from Human Resources and Recruitment Specialist as what are the available career opportunities for STEM Senior High School students.

Conclusion

This study implies developing a career framework for Senior High School students that aligns STEM skills with industry demands to bridge gap between education and workforce requirements. The career framework that lists down the skills needed in labor workforce could be the basis of the school in developing the program for STEM students ahead of time and prior to the work immersion. This is beneficial as well in conducting further research to identify specific areas of mismatch between STEM skills and industry demands, to tailor career guidance and counseling services for senior high school students. Furthermore, collaborating with industry partner to understand current and future skills requirements, and integrating this knowledge into career guidance and counseling services for senior high school students thru evaluating effectiveness of existing STEM education initiatives in preparing students for careers in industries with high demand for STEM skills, and identifying areas for improvement. Lastly, exploring the role of mentorship programs and internships in helping senior high school students develop necessary skills and competencies to meet industry demands in STEM related fields.

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